

Physico-chemical Studies on the Composition and Stability Constants of Zn(II), Cd(II) and Hg(II) DL-Valine Complexes

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DL-Valine [(CH₃)₂CH.CH(NH₂).COOH] complexes of divalent Zn, Cd and Hg have been investigated potentiometrically in aqueous 0.1 M NaClO₄ solution using Bjerrum-Calvin technique as modified by Irving and Rossotti at 20, 30 and 46°. The refinement of stability constants was made by the method of least square. The trend in the stability of these 1 : 1 metal complexes has been found to be :

Cd(II) forms only 1 : 1 complex at pH 3.35-8.55 and Zn(II) and Hg(II) 1 : 1 and 1 : 2 complexes at pH 2.90-8.20 and 3.46-7.75, respectively. The overall changes in thermodynamic parameters, ΔG, ΔH and ΔS, accompanying the complex formation have been determined.

SAXENA and co-workers¹⁻³ have studied metal complexes of amino acids which have found useful application in biological and pharmaceutical fields⁴. The present communication describes the chemistry of Zn(II), Cd(II) and Hg(II) complexes with DL-valine, their composition, stability constants and thermodynamic functions, accompanying the complexation reactions at different temperatures.

Experimental

DL-Valine [(CH₃)₂CH.CH(NH₂).COOH], referred herein as HA, was obtained from B. D. H., Poole, England. All other chemicals were of AnalaR grade. Solutions of metal ions were prepared in doubly distilled carbon dioxide free water. The experimental procedures were the same as reported earlier¹⁻³. pH measurements were made on 'EC' pH meter (5651) with glass calomel electrode assembly in a nitrogen atmosphere. The temperature of the cell was maintained by thermostat (U₃ type, German) having an accuracy of ±0.1°.

Results and Discussion

Stoichiometry : The composition of the complex formed during the interaction of metal ions with DL-valine was established by measuring the magnitude of proton displacement during the titration of ligand in the absence and presence of metal ion at different ratios (Fig. 1) indicating the complex formation which results in the lowering of buffer region due to proton displacement (Eq. 1).

where Mⁿ⁺ stands for Zn(II), Cd(II) and Hg(II).

When metal ion and ligand are mixed in the ratios 1 : 4, 1 : 2 and 1 : 1, the inflections are obtained at m=0.5, 1.0 and 2.0 respectively (m being the mole of NaOH per mole of HA). These inflections suggest the formation of MA⁺ and MA₂

Fig. 1. Potentiometric titrations of DL-valine (HA) in the absence and presence of Hg(II) with 0.1 M NaOH.

- Curve (a) : 4.0 mM HA
- Curve (b) : 4.0 mM HA + 1.0 mM Hg(II)
- Curve (c) : 4.0 mM HA + 2.0 mM Hg(II)
- Curve (d) : 4.0 mM HA + 4.0 mM Hg(II)

corresponding to 1 : 1 and 1 : 2 complexes respectively with considerable overlapping according to the following equations :

i.e. 1 : 1 and 1 : 2 complexes are formed simultaneously.

Stability constants: Stability constants of DL-valine $[(\text{CH}_2)_2\text{CH}(\text{NH}_2)\cdot\text{COOH}]$ complexes with divalent Zn, Cd and Hg were determined using Calvin-Bjerrum^{5,6} technique as modified by Irving and Rossotti⁷ and further refined by least square treatment.

At any pH, the value of free ligand concentration [A] was calculated from the relation (Fig. 2)

$$[A] = \frac{[\text{Ligand}]_{\text{total}} - [\text{ligand}]_{\text{bound}}}{(\text{H}^+/\text{K}_a) + 1} \quad \dots (5)$$

Fig. 2. Potentiometric titrations of DL-valine (HA) in the absence and presence of Hg(II) with 0.1 M NaOH

Curve a, c and e: 0.1 M NaClO₄ + 4.0 mM HClO₄ + 4.0 mM HA at 20, 30 and 40°, respectively.

Curve b, d and f: 0.1 M NaClO₄ + 4.0 mM HClO₄ + 4.0 mM HA + 1.0 mM Hg(II) at 20, 30 and 40°, respectively.

where K_a, the dissociation constant⁸ of HA, is 3.235×10^{-10} . The values of log K₁ and log K₂ were obtained from the formation curves (Fig. 3) at $\bar{n} = 0.5$ and 1.5 respectively.

The constants are best evaluated by the least square method

$$\frac{\bar{n}}{(\bar{n} - 1)[L]} = \frac{(2 - \bar{n})[L]}{(\bar{n} - 1)} K_1 K_2 - K_1 \quad \dots (6)$$

Fig. 3. Formation curves at 20, 30 and 40° for Hg(II) complexes of DL-valine (HA).

Curve a at 20°
Curve b at 30°
Curve c at 40°

The values of stability constants at various temperatures and by different methods are summarised in Table 1.

Thermodynamic functions: The values of overall changes in free energy, ΔG , enthalpy, ΔH , and entropy, ΔS , accompanying complex formation have been determined using the standard equations.

$$\Delta G = -RT \log \beta \quad (7)$$

$$\Delta H = \frac{2.305 R T_1 T_2 \log K_2 / \log K_1}{(T_2 - T_1)} \quad (8)$$

and

$$\Delta S = \frac{\Delta H - \Delta G}{T} \quad (9)$$

The values of thermodynamic parameters are given in Table 1.

Discussion

From a comparative account of the stability constants, it is evident that the values are slightly higher at 20° as compared to 30° and 40°, indicating that low temperature is favourable for complex formation. The trend in the stability of metal complexes is Zn(II) > Hg > Cd(II) in the case of

TABLE 1—METAL LIGAND STABILITY CONSTANTS AND THERMODYNAMIC FUNCTIONS FOR Zn(II), Cd(II) AND Hg(II) COMPLEXES OF DL-VALINE

System	Temperature °C	Bjerrum method		Least square method		ΔG KJ mol ⁻¹	ΔH KJ mol ⁻¹	ΔS (e.u.)
		log K ₁	log K ₂	log K ₁	log K			
Zn-HA	20	8.90	4.50	8.92	4.40	-74.5	—	—
	30	8.35	4.15	8.41	4.15	-72.2	-241.2	-133.3
	40	7.35	3.85	7.38	3.84	-66.6	—	—
Cd-HA	20	7.25	—	7.81	—	-43.4	—	—
	30	6.75	—	7.56	—	-43.4	-122.4	-62.3
	40	6.20	—	6.88	—	-40.8	—	—
Hg-HA	20	8.05	5.95	8.06	5.96	-77.9	—	—
	30	7.00	5.80	7.94	5.82	-79.0	-205.2	-99.5
	40	7.35	4.80	7.34	5.28	-74.9	—	—

Uncertainty limit for log K₁ = ± 0.4 and log K₂ = ± 0.3 ; for thermodynamic functions $\Delta G = \pm 0.3$ KJ mol⁻¹, $\Delta H = \pm 0.5$ KJ mol⁻¹, $\Delta S = \pm 4.5$ e.u.

1:1 which is in agreement with the accepted view that the stability of metal complexes depends on metallic nuclear charge (atomic number), its radius, and the screening effect of the electron present :

$$P = A \frac{Z - S}{r} \quad \dots (10)$$

where P is a polarising action of the metal ion, A is a proportionality coefficient, Z is the atomic number, S is the screening constant and r is the ionic radius.

The complex formation is a spontaneous process which is evident from the negative values of ΔG ; the negative values of ΔH also ensure that the reaction is exothermic.

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